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October 7th, 2019

Editorial

Dear supporter,

As announced last August 20, ENERGY-X and SUNRISE have started a joint cooperation and plan to merge in a larger initiative, by the end of the CSA projects, in February 2020.

We share common goals for developing approaches for the storage of renewable energy (solar and wind) through its conversion to fuels and commodity chemicals using abundant molecules such as carbon dioxide, water and nitrogen. Our cooperation aims at uniting efforts at European level by setting a large-scale initiative to develop sustainable alternatives to the use of fossil fuels, contributing to the COP21 Paris Agreement.

We are already working on joint actions and we need a new name for our next joint initiative that shows our common vision and shared strengths. So far, we have been using the temporarily name SUNERGY. Could you think about a different one? We will be delighted to hear your name proposal(s)! Please let us know yours by contacting us at contact@sunriseaction.eu and/or contact@energy-x.eu by October 14, 2019.

The SUNRISE Team

SUNRISE and ENERGY-X Announce a Joint Cooperation at Europacat 2019

Joint Press Release

Representatives from the EU Horizon 2020 Coordination and Support Actions (CSAs) SUNRISE and ENERGY-X announced their joint cooperation on August 20, 2019 during the...

Upcoming Events

SUNRISE France Stakeholder Workshop

Following other previous national workshops, such as the **Italian**, **Polish** and **Swiss** ones, We are pleased to invite you to the SUNRISE and ENERGY-X Initiatives Workshop in France, an event...

SUNRISE Consortium & Mission Innovation Meeting in Brussels

The members of the SUNRISE Consortium will address the joint

cooperation between ENERGY-X and SUNRISE. Besides, there will be a gathering with Mission Innovation where...

Opportunities in the Field

Extra € 45.4 million for FETPROACT-EIC-05-2019 and FETPROACT-EIC-06-201

Delayed deadline: November 13, 2019

The Commission is currently discussing changes to the 2019 Enhanced European Innovation Council (EIC) Workprogramme to allocate...

EIC prize: Fuel from the Sun, Artificial Photosynthesis

Deadline: first quarter, 2021

The challenge is to build a fully functional, bench-scale prototype of an artificial photosynthesis based system which can...

Second Trimester Highlights

Towards a Circular Economy: Video interview with Nicola Armaroli

"When we use something we normally throw it away. This is the linear economy, and this means that the product has an end of life. This is not good. Our economy cannot go this way..."

SUNRISE Infographics: Breaking down the circular economy

What does 'circular economy' stand for? Why is it important? How can we incorporate it in our daily lives? Awareness of the importance of the circular economy and its role towards...

SUNRISE Poster wins the 'Best Poster Award' at ICCDU 2019

We are very happy to announce that SUNRISE's poster won the 'Best Poster Award'! We would like to thank ICCDU organizers for providing us with the opportunity to showcase our project...

Hervé Bercegol, SUNRISE deputy coordinator: "Storing renewable energy in molecules is the most convenient solution"

A few months ago, Lilo Bolen from WEKA Industrie Medien did an interview with Hervé Bercegol about SUNRISE. Learn more about our deputy coordinator views on the project and...

SUNRISE on the road: Towards a circular and secular economy in South Africa

On July 30, 2019 the SUNRISE project was presented by the SUNRISE partner Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Science and Technology (Empa)'s Dr. Artur Braun at the University...

“Manufacturing processes will underpin the green transition now and in the future”: An interview with John Mathews

Western industrialism has achieved miracles, promoting unprecedented levels of prosperity and raising millions around the world out of poverty. But as China, India and other industrializing...

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